

Event title	Getting started with deep learning
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	21/07/2021
Time of event	12 - 1pm AEST
Topic description	<p>Are you wondering what deep learning is and how it might be useful in your research? This high level overview introduces deep learning 'in a nutshell' and provides tips on which concepts and skills you will need to know to build a deep learning application. The presentation also provides pointers to various resources you can use to get started in deep learning.</p> <p>The webinar is followed by a short Q&A session.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/deep-learning-titus
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	<p>Machine learning http://edamontology.org/topic_3474 Deep learning Neural networks</p>
Contact	Melissa Burke melissa@biocommons.org.au
Audience	Complete beginners in machine learning, deep learning, or programming, who want to investigate the potential application of AI systems in their research.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe the concepts of deep learning at a high level • Identify steps for getting started with deep learning • List resources for learning more about deep learning

Lead Trainer	Dr Titus Tang, Senior Deep Learning Engineer, Data Science and AI Platform, Monash University
Facilitators	Not applicable
Related work	Not applicable